

The Impact of Cultural Milieu In Developing Second Language Awareness: Towards An Intercultural Shelter of Mind

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ABSTRACT : The article is dealt with the importance of culture in developing second language awareness. Students' identification with, and maintenance of their native language and culture can have a positive influence on learning a second culture, more specifically, on learning English as a second language. The process of acquiring a second language is the process of transcreating one culture into another. Culture, a vibrant resource, represents hidden curriculum in second language teaching. The present study explores that language and culture are inseparable that constitute a single universe we experience.

Keywords : Culture, English Language Teaching, ESL, Intercultural competence, classroom strategies.

Introduction

Language, as we know, is not only a tacit and formal system of sounds, words, and syntactical structures, language also sensitizes the vibrant domain of human interaction. Language is the abode of being; it is the fundamental signs of our humanity. Language is the palette from which people colour their lives and culture. Language is a social phenomenon and language learning is therefore a social

activity. Learning is not a neat, linear process. It is not like laying a single railway line across an open plane. A child learns a language with reference to various socio-cultural contexts. Language learning does not entail only knowing the language in L_1 or L_2 , but also knowing how to use language in situations and contexts. The process of acquiring a second language is thus the process of transcreating one culture into another. Culture is the software of the mind,

without which human behaviour is random, unpredictable and meaningless. While learning a second/foreign language, every native speaker assimilates his individual and social experiences which are simply the reflection of his own culture. A child learning a language is learning about the world, about how it is organized and how it works. Language is to be interpreted in terms of culture. Culture is far more than a mere catalogue of rituals and beliefs; it is the heart beat of our existence, something which makes life worth living.

The Culture Defined:

Agatha Christie in 'Hickory Dickory Death' presented an African student in London: 'All this morning', said Akibombo mournfully, 'I have been much disturbed. I can not answer my professor's questions good at all. He is not pleased at me. He says to me that I copy large bits out of books and do not think for myself. But I am here to acquire wisdom from much books and it seems to me that they say better in the books than the way I put it, because I have not good command of the English'. (1955:149-50). Agatha depicted the picture of inability of a student in comprehending a foreign or second language. But what exists behind the curtain is simply a psychological dearth caused by cultural differences. It is culture that determines learning spectrum. The relationship between language and mind is essential to an understanding of culture as it affects language learning. Then the inevitable question that appears is that, what does culture mean? Culture means a heightened state of mind, a cultivated code of conduct that every individual should aspire to touch. Culture may be considered as an integrated pattern of human behaviour that includes thoughts, communications, languages, practices, beliefs,

values, customs, rituals, relationships and expected behaviour of a racial, ethnic, religious or social group; and the ability to transmit the above to succeeding generations. Culture influences all aspect of human behaviour. It refers to the shared attributes of one group.

One soul Inhabiting Two Bodies: Language and Culture

A second language learner's understanding of a second culture is fundamentally affected by his or her culturally- defined worldview, beliefs, affective disposition and presuppositions. These beliefs and presuppositions having been prompted by culture-learning (native as well as foreign) are significantly a must for the pedagogical implications in second language teaching and learning. Since language is used in social exchanges, the feelings, attitudes and motivations of learners in relation to the target language itself, to the speakers of the language and above all, to the culture, will affect how learners respond to the input to which they are exposed. In other words, these affective variables will determine the rate and degree of second language learning. Culture and language are inseparable and constitute "a single universe or domain of experience" (Kramsch, 1991, p. 217). Cultural awareness and the learning of a second culture can only aid the attaining of second language proficiency. Culture, in fact, represents hidden curriculum in second language teaching. If we have a look at Raymond Williams (1961: 41-50), we can see three important ways of thinking about culture:

- * Culture as the ethos, the embodiment of perpetual values and we have to cope up with those values as the torch of existence.

- * Culture as most reliable documentary in which human thought, belief, language, convention,, experience are our recorded as authentic source.
- * Culture as social, as a way of life in which the structure of feeling of a social group should be valued.

Language is a part of its speakers' culture, it is not a separate aspect of life. The two are intertwined and develop in concert, with neither of them being cause nor effect. Language is the most important thing that gives us identity. It is in the domain of culture that we think, express ourselves, articulate our aspirations and anxieties. It is our culture that distinguishes us, and defines our humanity. No wonder, culture remains an intimate zone. We breathe and smell our culture. It is this emotive engagement with our culture that also causes an acute anxiety. We often feel that if we lose our culture, our identity will be at stake. Language is loved and celebrated as a marker of

identity, as a symbol of "I-ness", 'we-ness', 'us-ness'. Language does not focus one-dimensional identity; on the contrary, identity is a dynamic, multilayered social process rather than an inborn trait. Cultural constructs that govern individual's sky of beliefs and values are often reflected in communicative interactions. Culture is transmitted from one generation to the next through language. The influence of culture on language and language on culture are difficult to untwine. Hence, language should be conceptualized as symbiotic part of society, culture and psyche. Spolsky (1989) presents the

following model of second language learning in a specific socio-cultural milieu.

Creating the Vision: Teaching Culture

In contemporary language classrooms, teachers are expected to integrate cultural components because language teaching has been influenced by a significantly different perspectives on culture itself. These perspectives come from the social sciences. McKay (2002) observed that culture influences language teaching in two ways: linguistic and pedagogical. Linguistically, it espouses the semantic, pragmatic, and discourse analysis. Pedagogically, it affects the choice of the language materials because cultural content of the language materials and the cultural basis of the teaching methodology are to be taken into consideration while deciding upon the language materials. For example, while some text books in vernacular provide examples and analogies from native culture in teaching English as second language. The mother-tongue need not be an interloper but a resource. We can speak of a “cognitive academic linguistic proficiency” as language and thinking skill that build on the basis of a child’s spontaneous knowledge of language which is culturally- defined.

The communicative model is based on this understanding of the relationship between language and culture. Linguistic, discourse, sociolinguistic, and strategic competence incorporate facets of culture, and the development of these competences is intertwined with the development of cultural awareness. “The exquisite connection between the culture that is lived and the language that is spoken, can only be realized by those who possess a knowledge of both “. (National Standards in Foreign Language Education Project, 1999,p.

47). Culture classes have a humanizing and a motivating effect on the language learner and the learning process. They help learners observe similarities and differences among various cultural groups. Today, most of L₂ students around the world live in a monolingual and monocultural environment. The process of acquiring a second culture has been studied from a number of perspectives. Acculturation, the gradual adaption to the target language without necessarily forsaking one’s native language identity, has been very often proposed as a model for the learners entering into a new culture.

But the process of becoming adapted to a new culture, a reorientation of thinking and feeling is not simply a one way process. The process of acculturation runs even deeper when language appears into the purview. As language is the means for communication among members of a culture, a person’s worldview, self-identity, his system of thinking, feeling and communicating may be disrupted by a change from one culture to another. Persons, under such circumstances, very often experience a culture shock that reflects his anxiety and nervousness with cultural differences. On the other hand, learning a second culture, if it is embedded with ethnocentric overtones, if it is compared and contrasted with that of the native culture, then, culture helps in developing second language awareness among learners. This broadened awareness touches all dimensions of life: individual, social, geographic, historical, artistic, anthropological aspect of the target society.

It is now broadly accepted throughout the world that learning a second language is not simply mastering an objects of academic study but is more appropriately focused on learning a means of communication. Communication in real

situations is never out of context. As culture is a part of most contexts, communication is rarely culture-free. Thus, it is now increasingly recognized that language learning and learning about target culture cannot realistically be separated. Following this line of thinking, it can be said that communicative competence is to be integrated into intercultural competence which is seen in social effectiveness. "The current dedication to the development of the communicative competence of language learners mandates the development of intercultural communicative skills and an understanding of the processes of culture learning on the part of students and teachers alike". Damen (1987, p.xiv).

In teaching culture, we presume that teachers and learners should take a more reflective or ethnographic stance towards cultural content and methodology, in order to raise their awareness of intercultural issues. It would obviously be a useful development if more text books include explicit intercultural elements and if teachers are more conscious of intercultural competence. In this way, the method determines the use of the medium in a multicultural classroom, because medium and method are culturally interdependent. They reflect each other in a half-of-mirrors effect. Intercultural competence not only encourages the consciousness of one's identity, but also encourages the awareness of others' identities. As Meyer (1991, p. 137) says, "Intercultural competence includes the capacity of stabilizing one's self-identity in the process of cross-cultural mediation, and of helping other people to stabilize their self-identity".

Both social psychologists and social constructivists espouse the view that knowledge

evolves through a process of negotiation within a discourse community. Thus knowledge is a social rather than an individual product. Its construction and creation is 'shared' and entails a dialectical interplay rather than being a solely individual experience. Language learning, in both learners' own and target culture, enables the teacher to orient the learners' conceptual constructions. Teaching language is thus teaching culture. A culture class is significantly beneficial in terms of developing language skills, raising cultural awareness, changing attitudes towards native and target societies and contributing a lot to the teaching profession. What constitutes effective teaching and learning is often based on the socialization processes and the internalization of roles and expectations that teachers and learners take for granted. These are closely intertwined with attitudes, values, and beliefs that underlie the teaching of culture. To be effective and to help learners achieve intercultural competence, the teaching and learning of culture need to become a dialogue between the source and the target culture. In making the entire pursuit learner-friendly, the role of teacher with intercultural competence is so crucial, so significant that without which, the entire project might be next to nothing. An ethnographic stance of both teachers and learners can only promote an awareness of their own and others' identities that can lead to creating better teaching materials and methods.

A warm feeling of being close: Metacognition and Culture

Many learners and teachers view language only as a communication toll a method men use to indicate the objects and ideas of their physical and social world. In this view, learning a foreign or second language is the simple

process of substituting words and rules to get the same meaning with a different tool. This kind of thinking leads to such a situation where learners are able to speak a foreign language fluently, but they don't understand the social or philosophical content of that language. Under such circumstances, we need to understand more completely the cultural dimension of language. Language does serve as a toll for communication, but in addition it is a "system of representation" for perception and thinking. This function of language guides our formation of concepts, thinking abilities; it directs how we experience reality.

Extensive research that goes deeper into learning strategies has been carried out by O'Malley and Chamot (1990) within an overall modal of L₂ learning based on cognitive psychology. They have identified three main types of strategy used by L₂ students:

1. Metacognitive strategies
2. Cognitive strategies
3. Social strategies

Among the three types of strategy, mentioned above, there is a close link between metacognition and culture. Metacognitive strategies, that is, organizing and evaluating knowledge by preparing in advance what is going to come up in the next class. Metacognition can be defined as thinking about thinking. The use of metacognitive strategies ignites one's thinking and can lead to more profound learning and improved performance, especially among learners who are involved in an intercultural set-up, because culture, we know, is a way of life, the context within which we exist, think, feel and relate others, within which the thought process gets its reflection in the intercultural

mirrors. It is important that teachers teach their students metacognitive skills in addition to cognitive skills. Rather than focus learners' attention solely on learning the language, second language teachers can help learners learn to think about what happens during the language learning process in reality, how culture affects learners' thinking skills. The learners, in this way, may internalize the socio-cultural artefacts and become more culturally autonomous. Strong metacognitive skills empower second language learners. So, the metacognitive skills of learners are developed in association with social interaction which is culturally-driven.

One of the most influential models since the early 1990s has been sociocultural theory, which emphasises the importance of interaction from a rather different perspective. This theory takes its starting point from the works of Lev Vygotsky. The distinctive aspect of Vygotsky's zone of proximal development (ZPD) is that the gap between the learners' current state and their future knowledge is bridged by assistance from others; learning demands sociocultural interactions so that the learner can internalize knowledge out of external action. Any new function appears twice: first, on the sociocultural level, and later on the individual level; first, 'between' people (interpsychological) and then 'inside' the child (intrapsychological). This means the only good learning is that which is in advance of development. The ZPD has been developed in SLA sociocultural theory far beyond Vygotsky's original interpretation. In particular, social assistance is interpreted through the concept of scaffolding, the process that assists the learner in getting to the next point in development.

Like the interaction hypothesis, sociocultural theory bases itself on the dialogue that learners encounter in the classroom. Its essence is what Merrill Swain (2000 : 102) calls ‘collaborative dialogue’ – ‘dialogue in which speakers are engaged in problem solving and knowledge building’. Hence, it is not the dialogue of the interaction hypothesis in which people exchange information, that is, communication, but an educational dialogue in which people create new knowledge, that is, constructive learning. The teaching of culture implicitly or explicitly permeates the teaching of social interaction, and the spoken and the written language. Byram and Morgan (1994, p. 43) state that “Learners are ‘committed’ to their culture and to deny any part of it is to deny something within their own being’. This conceptualization of sociocultural reflection is predominantly applicable in learning the first language (mother tongue) and the second language as well.

In developing learners’ metacognitive skill in assistance with culture (both native and target), the learners’ strategies should have a *laissez-faire* attitude. The teacher in this situation will offer the cultural input that will motivate the learners. Learning takes place in the learners’ minds in ways that teachers cannot control. Here learning is autonomous. By becoming autonomous, the learners gradually replace the belief that they are ‘consumers’ of language with the belief that they can be ‘producers’ of their own learning programme.

The Sensitive Corridor: Indian Panorama

The traditional mind-set of most of the Indians about English language may be assimilated with that of our traditional attitude towards a ‘cow’. Both the cow and the English language in India are held in reverence. Cow is

domesticated by many Indians with a touch of worship that it will bring them infinite riches of the “Paraloka’, the unseen, other world in the distant future. The worship of English is also expected to bring immense wealth of this world in the ‘ihaloka’, the here and now. But what is interestingly striking is that neither English, nor a cow are properly taken care of; though we do not let them die in peace. We don’t want to nurture them for their good health and congenial habitat. Likewise, we never feel any cultural empathy with English; we just need English for our material prosperity and nothing else. English Language Teaching (ELT) in India has been suffering from the disease of ‘shadow mind’— a virtual, inauthentic Indian mind functioning under the colonial hangover. This is due to the incongruous and incomplete mind-set of the Indians about ELT in which culture-specific pedagogy remains a mirage all along.

There remains another story on the other side of the canvas, i.e., the recently developed attitude to English language in India. The impact of Globalization, the Liberalization of the economy, the opening of the worldwide market, the job-opportunities have created an ‘English advantage’ in contemporary India. This sudden English boom has become India’s selling point in the national as well as international market. So, the simultaneous existence of so-called artificial light and original darkness, so-called success and genuine pathos go hand in hand in English Language Teaching in India. English language, in our country, is a totem, a weapon bristling with class bias and elitist thorns. To some, it is a portal, a door; to others, it is a wall, stony and nightmarish.

To avoid such sort of circumstances, English language teachers can be more deliberate in

helping students learn to experience reality in a new way. A ‘culture-contrast’ approach may be useful in this regard, including the following steps:

1. Inform learners about how their native language (mother-tongue) is related to basic values, beliefs, thought-patterns, and social action in their own culture.
2. Compare native language-culture patterns to those of the new language culture. Look especially for concepts and structures in the target language that do not exist in the native language.
3. Assess achievement not just in terms of vocabulary and grammar but also in the pragmatic dimensions of culturally appropriate social judgment and decision-making.

More cultural input in the native and target language will have to be incorporated in school curriculum. The role of teachers’ intercultural competence in relating entire general school education to its specific cultural context becomes very crucial. The role of the teacher as cultural accommodator and mediator is fundamental in promoting students’ learning.

In my end is my beginning

What we have come across is that a culture-focussed dimension of teaching English as a second language is not only advantageous to the learners, but also helps them learn their native language well. Cultural values are both reflected by and carried through language. Even while recognizing that the vast societal context shapes how and what of we epitomize culture in the classroom, we must believe that classrooms can be a space from which we creatively construct, and redefine culture. The language and culture

classes aim at improving one’s understanding of the language and the people who speak it. It has become axiomatic to draw attention to the inextricable bond between language and culture. A learner is a cultural being with a cultural perspective on the world, including culture-specific expectations of the classroom and learning processes. The positive attitude towards the culture of the target language is a favourable resource in language learning.

Training to be prospective teachers of English, for students of ELT studying English culture, is not an arbitrary but a necessary activity. It may point out opportunities for teachers to use their own spontaneous imagination. Thus, learning a second language ultimately becomes learning to be another social person. This has led many researchers into teacher effectiveness to emphasise that the creation and maintenance of a pro-culture positive classroom climate is essential in producing optimum learning. Therefore, in order to develop teacher’s intercultural competence in a multilingual setting, five pragmatic considerations are to be followed in continuance with the teaching/learning process:

1. teacher analysis of culturally-viable contexts,
2. cognitive and metacognitive awareness skills,
3. receptive/integrative skills,
4. controlled productive skills, and
5. free integrated practice.

The innovative teachers must be inclined to:

- develop learners’ culture-based communicative skills.

- assist the learners in understanding the linguistic and behavioural patterns of both the target and the native culture at a more conscious level.
- develop the intercultural competence of the teaching communities.
- adopt a wider perspective in the perception of the reality.
- develop teachers' metacognitive strategies in order to develop learners' thinking skill.

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